

PROBLEMS FACED BY CHILDREN IN READING – CAUSES AND REMEDIES

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What is Reading?

Reading behavior is receiving communication, making discriminative responses to graphic symbols and decoding graphic symbols to speech (Gibson). Reading may be defined as the act of receiving meaning from a written form. It is the ability to interpret linguistic sounds in their graphic and symbolic representation. Reading is a complex cognitive process of decoding symbols in order to construct or derive meaning. Like all language, it is a complex interaction between the text and the reader which is shaped by the reader's prior knowledge, experiences, attitude, and language community which is culturally and socially situated. The reading process requires continuous practice, development, and refinement.

It is one of the fundamental skills in language learning. It is a receptive skill. It is a means of fixing firmly the language items which have already been learnt by the child as a part of listening and speaking.

Reading is a complex "cognitive process" of decoding symbols in order to construct or derive meaning. Reading is a means of language acquisition, communication, and of sharing information and ideas. Like all languages, it is a complex interaction between the text and the reader which is shaped by the reader's prior knowledge, experiences, attitude, and language community which is culturally and socially situated.

According to Sounerchein, "Reading is thinking under the stimulus of the printed.

According to Goodman, "Reading is psycholinguistic guessing game. According to

Smith, “Reading is an act of communication in which information is transferred from a transmitter to a receiver. Gray is of the view that reading process enables the reader to understand the text at three levels: first, the purely literal responding to the graphic signals only with little depth of understanding; the second level at which the reader recognizes the author’s meaning, and the third level where the reader’s own personal experiences and judgments influence his response to the text.”

CAUSES

- (1) **Does not always recognize start or end sounds:-** Many children know their letter sounds , but cannot recognize these sounds when sounding out words.
- (2) **Guesses, mispronounces or skips words while reading:-** Many children will skip words when reading , preferring to read the words they recognize first and fill in the unknown words later . Or if they cannot decode the word, they will guess.
- (3) **Forgets words even right after being helped:-** Many children frustrate their parents and teachers by failing to recognize the same word on the same or next page , within a minute of two or receiving help with the word earlier.
- (4) **Cannot spell:** - NO doubt, spelling rules, conventions , learn , however ,spelling rules,Conventions and expectations that take to learn, however, spelling in the early grades is Only concern if your child struggles with regular, phonetic words. There is more to stake Than just spelling accuracy. Recognition of spelling patterns is a big part of how the brain Reads. Spelling is a key decoding skill.
- (5) **Resists reading:** - Many children with reading difficulties start to resist reading out loud to their parents. Furthermore, they become easily distracted in reading times in school.
- (6) **Slow reader:** - Many students learn to decode by middle school, but they read slowly, which impacts homework efficiency and test taking. Slow reading also orders interest in Reading.

(6) Cannot read for long period: - Reading stamina is an important reading skill. Many Children with reading problems can only read for a few minutes at a time. This makes it Difficult to get through assigned material and the shortened periods cut down on reading Practice.

(8) Does not enjoy reading: - Many students do not enjoy text books, assigned texts, Novels, newspapers, and magazines.

(9) Eyesight problem: - Many children have eyesight problem. Due to this problem They have difficulties in reading.

(10) Lack of knowledge: - Students do not have proper knowledge due to which they Face problems in reading.

(11)No proper arrangements of lights: - In some classes there are no proper arrangements of lights, so the students face difficulty to see the letter and read them.

(12) Misprint: - Children face problems while reading if the words and sentences are not Properly Printed.

(13) Lack of self confidence: - Those students who do not have confidence, they cannot Read anything in front of others. They face difficulties to read in front of others.

(14) Lack of Concentration: - Lack of concentration causes distraction in reading. if there Is no proper concentration while reading then it is useless to read anything?

(15) Hesitation: - Hesitation is one of the causes of reading. Children usually hesitate to speak in front of others. They think that if something gets wrong or if there occurs any Mistake in pronunciation, others may laugh at them.

(16) Hearing Problem: - Some children have hearing problem due to which they cannot Hear the letters, words and sentences properly and due to which they cannot read these Letter, words and sentences.

(17) Environment: - Environment is very important while reading. If there is no proper Environment, children can face difficulties in reading.

(18) Lack of interest: - Lack of reading interest can be caused by some factors such as rare Place, rare, interesting books etc.

(19) Proper Ventilation:-No proper ventilation is major problem of poor reading.

(20) No reading competition are organise in the school:-Most of the school avoid reading competitions

REMEDIES: -

(1) Take breaks: - Cognitive fatigue can lead to all of the aforementioned problems and to other problems as well. If you do not rest your mind, you will likely get fatigued and it will cost you points.

(2) Trace your place: - children can mark their place either by pointing to each word as they read it, or by placing a sheet of paper underneath the line they are reading. Pointing To each word with a pencil or their finger can help their eye see where it should be Reading. Placing a paper under the line they are reading can help them to move smoothly from one line to the next.

(3) Read aloud: - If a child is in his own room, he can actually say each word aloud. Reading aloud can help him stay focused, understand better, and remember what He is reading.

(4) Read carefully and deliberately: - Take your time when you are reading. Focus your Attention on each word and be sure that you read what is written.

(5) Talk about double meaning words: - Talk about words that have double meanings, and Make a list as many words that you can think of that have multiple meanings.

(6) Uncover misspelled words: - If spelling is a problem, go through the students notebooks Handouts to uncover commonly misspelled words. Place each word on a sing page, and inventing memory strategies that will help the student recall the correct spelling.

(7) **Play search games:** - Play search games with words and letters that are confusing. For Instance, if a young learner mixes up the letters banded, provide a magazine, newspaper, other print out and ask them to circle all the letter b's. They do not have to read the text. They will just be scanning for the latter or word.

(8) **Proper Environment:-** Provide proper environment to the children at school and homes So that they may not face any difficulty in reading.

(9) **Proper knowledge:** - Before reading, children must be given proper knowledge about the letter or words.

(10) **Proper arrangement of lights:** - There should be proper arrangement of light, so that a Reader or a child can see the words properly without any difficulty.

(11) **Motivation:** - Teacher and parents should motivate a child while they are reading something. This can improve his reading skill.

(12) **Full concentration:** - While reading, a child's mind should concentrate on what he is Reading. There should not be anything which distracts his mind. TO conclude, we can say that there are many problems which the children have to face while reading texts. These problems occur due to many causes, some of them are- Hesitation, cannot spell, slow reader, eyesight problem, Misprint, etc. If there are some causes Then there are also some remedies with the help of which the students can develop their reading Skill. Some of the remedies are- motivation, full concentration, proper environment, proper Knowledge, etc.